

CASE STUDY ON THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE PANDEMIC ON THE SPECIFIC RISKS OF A PATHOLOGICAL ANATOMY SERVICE IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

Purpose – *The good management of these risks, as well as the supported control, aim to make the specific activities of pathological anatomy services more efficient by identifying the incidence and factors that can create managerial risks and lead to unfavorable events or consequences.*

Methodology/approach – *The research presents an approach to a less investigated field from the point of view of managerial risks. The approach is theoretical and at the same time practical through a case study.*

Findings – *The observed changes had a direct effect on the patients but also on the medical staff.*

Limitations/implications of the research – *The present research was carried out in a pathological anatomy laboratory within a public hospital in Romania*

Originality – *Realization of an original synthesis regarding the managerial risks specific to a pathological anatomy service, which represents a novelty in the field of knowledge at the national and European level.*

Key words: *risk, management, pathological anatomy*

Introduction

Managerial risks in pathological anatomy services in public hospitals in Romania represent the important factor in the management of medical and sanitary activities as well as in pathological anatomy services.

The good management and control of these risks are aimed at streamlining the specific activities of pathological anatomy services by identifying the incidence and factors that can create adverse events or consequences.

Of course, the Covid 19 pandemic has strongly affected the working capacity of these services and the research on how the awareness of managerial and clinical risks has influenced or not the activity of pathological anatomy laboratories is a strictly current topic and the new data created by this situation changes substantially knowledge and working methodology in case of unwanted events.

The present research carries out a theoretical analysis of all the managerial and clinical risks identified in the pathological anatomy services in the pre-pandemic, pandemic and post-pandemic periods and highlights, through a case study at a specialized unit, the practical methods adopted by the leaders of the health units and of the managers of pathological anatomy laboratories to ensure the functioning of the respective services within the parameters.

In the post-pandemic context, one can observe a much deeper interest in the management of managerial risks, which have affected this segment of medicine, and the adopted measures present a reorientation towards a technological, qualitative but also economic reconfiguration, due to the awareness of the much more complex specific environment, changeable, often unpredictable.

Research methodology: the research carried out by the authors represents an approach in a less investigated field from the point of view of managerial risks, however, and in which the pandemic

condition has had a strong impact. The research methodology is based on two components: one based on a theoretical study from the specialized literature on the consequences of the pandemic in health, and one in which a case study is carried out on the managerial methods adopted in a specialized unit.

The theoretical study based on documentary research on the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic in the field of health

The influence of the pandemic on the health system, a significant factor in the evolution of the public health system.

The pandemic that hit worldwide demonstrated that the limits of the health system could be exceeded, and all efforts of any kind, whether human or material, led to its reinvention.

Although the health systems, regardless of their nature, some more performing, which adapted to people's needs, others did not overcome their condition of "primitive systems", all were put in unprecedented situations, and were obliged" to adapt to the new medical emergency requirements.

Being an unprecedented situation, involvement and sacrifice had a decisive role, elements that characterized the factors involved. In this context, numerous public and private entities took part in the fight against the pandemic: starting from high-level involvement - governments, respectively the sustained interest of EU states, to industry, the medical, scientific field, research and ordinary citizens, they all put in immeasurable efforts.

The pandemic situation has visibly influenced society, but the center of gravity was the health system that was taken unprepared and that brought to light the disastrous situation that dates back decades and that health reforms seem to not exist.

At the global level, solidarity is the key word, the World Health Organization, together with the EU and all the other countries of the world, had an exceptional collaboration, and which set in motion all the instruments to combat this crisis.

It is known that the coronavirus pandemic was a real threat at the global level to the health of the population as well as at the financial, behavioral and why not change of mentality and priorities, in other words, the "Coronavirus" affects social security.

With all the efforts made by world public entities, in combating the terrible disease, several successful models have been marked on the "pandemic map", such as that of: China, Germany, South Korea, but it is also worth noting the Swedish model which approves of the casual distancing in which society is not corseted. About the terrible disease, both the international mass media and the written press emphasized the aggressiveness of the virus and that this disease is considered an emergency, but also how unprepared the health system was, including the Chinese one, as reported in an article published in the American Journal of Public Health (Bouey, 2020).

I.Chifu (2020), shows that it occurs as sudden movements of evolution which of course is perceived as a threat in terms of basic values;

The Journal of Asian Finance, economics and Business, highlights through an empirical study, the major changes in the purchase of medical products during the pandemic crisis, "the trend towards the marketing of health products to increase public attention to health values has increased during the Covid-19 pandemic". (Hidayat, Wibowo, Gunawan, Dewi, Wijayaningtyas, 2021)

A major contribution was made by all the states of the world in the management of the pandemic in which the decision-makers had an unexpected involvement in the good sense of the word, and this emerges from the work of E. Anatol (2012) The concept of global health from the perspective of the globalization phenomenon.

There are many critical voices that show us how the health crisis generated by Covid-19 has revealed the incapacity of international governance, starting with the WHO. (Dutu, 2022)

In all this maelstrom, in which no one knew what tomorrow would bring, important leaps were also highlighted, such as that of the digitalization of the medical field, more correctly said, the pandemic helped the evolution of digitalization in the health field. However, the pandemic had a motivational role

regarding the transition from a poorly computerized health system to a system compatible with the latest, D. B. Abrudan (2022) in the work "Elements of leadership in medical services" (Abrudan, Boşcai, Popovic, 2022), suggests that the adoption of the smart hospital model, where the patient finds himself in harmony with modern technology, would be indicated.

In the specialized literature, numerous articles have appeared in which the factors that have negatively influenced society are presented. Among these factors, we can primarily highlight the stress factors and their consequences, including at work, and here I am referring to the medical body in particular, which not infrequently led to the onset of burnout syndrome. This pandemic affected the entire social system rapidly, the transmission route being airborne, they affected many lives, as reported by J. Marwha and K. Shah (2022).

Also in this way remarkable efforts have been made to find the right treatment, including the testing of some drugs, this is evidenced by numerous international papers.

Classification of managerial and clinical risks in the Pathological Anatomy laboratory

Risk, condition sine - qua - non!

According to L. Marian (2001), "the risk as the possibility of an unwanted event with a multitude of consequences", which harms the person, either patient or medical staff, we can draw the conclusion that risks in hospitals derive from certain situations with triangular configuration that targets both procedural/medical technology, relational/human and managerial space.

The realization of a coherent management in terms of risks does not mean only the simple inventory of risks, but involves a series of technical-managerial maneuvers based on specific techniques that require prior analysis of everything that means exposure to risk, and the origin of the specific management these situations represent the identification of risk sources.

The identification of risks stipulated in the Risk Management Methodology, represents the primary condition, is to define the level of risk tolerance, assess the probability of risks, establish the impact and exposure to risk, and finally to establish and adopt the appropriate strategy.

This scientific approach, originating from the competitive economy, is also successfully applied in health, respectively in pathological anatomy services. Of course, being a hospital environment, all the focus falls on the medical act, which has certain well-established procedures and for which the risk categories are identified clinical, but should not be ignored the activities of management, planning, organization, management and control of medical units that have a major impact on the final results and the successful fulfillment of the system's objectives.

Pathological anatomy being a laboratory where the histopathological diagnosis is awaited with major emotions and great interest by the patient, tends towards a real "emancipation" which can be defined as a self-overcoming, a progress, a reinvention in front of the patient by introducing some parameters of professionalism, accuracy, promptness and efficiency. All these parameters are dependent on a more comprehensive awareness of the managerial risks specific to health facilities both in normal periods but especially in crisis ones. Thus, following the theoretical research carried out, it is highlighted that in pathological anatomy services there are risks falling into two categories, clinical risks and managerial risks.

Clinical risks specific to pathological anatomy services (adapted from V. Cepoi)

A cataloging of clinical and professional risks was carried out by V. Cepoi (2017), it shows that the health sector, being one of the largest sectors of activity in Europe, employs approximately 10% of EU employees, where the frequency of work accidents is somewhere at 34%. Of course, any healthcare unit with a well-developed management wants to increase patient safety, it is based on the management of clinical risks that are generated primarily by the quality of medical procedures and their compliance. (Cepoi, 2017)

Clinical risk is an unwanted event directed at the patient and affecting the patient's interests. These risks categorically influence:

- Extending the duration to receive a histopathological diagnosis;
- Aggravation of the patient's health condition;
- Inability to overcome the disease state;
- Prolongation of the illness;
- Death of the patient.

In this table (table no. 1) the clinical risks mentioned by Cepoi (2017) and found by the authors of the paper in the pathological anatomy services in Romania can be found in the categories that the present paper only names.

Table no. 1. Classification of risks in pathological anatomy services - Adaptation of clinical risks according to V. Cepoi

Risk	Clinical risk
Risk of misidentifying the patient	The risk of worsening the mental state of patients/relatives
The risk of not being able to transport biological samples correctly	The risk of damaging the biological sample; -The risk of damaging the accompanying documents; - The risk of not receiving the results on time
Risk of not being able to release paraffin blocks and slides	- The risk of having no concordance between the initial result and the one released at the 2nd opinion
The risk of employee illness	The risk of staff illness;
Risk of personal injury	The risk of staff illness;
The production of biological waste (fluids, tissues, human cells and organs) and chemical waste (formalin, alcohol, xylene, etc.)	The risk of staff illness;
The risk of having unsatisfied patients	The risk of having untreated patients
The risk of finalizing the histopathological results outside the deadline provided by law	The risk of worsening the disease; The risk of complications; The risk of death
Risk of mishandling biological samples and accompanying documents	- The risk of illness and injury
The risk of misunderstanding the employee-patient (belonging) message,	- The risk of worsening the mental state of patients/relatives
Risk of providing data without consent or legal approval	- The risk of not contributing to the patient's mental well-being
The risk of drafting and drafting documents erroneously	- the risk of wrong treatment
The risk of entering incorrect or delayed data into the computer system	- treatment delay
The risk of not having a consistent supply	- The risk of not receiving treatment on time
The risk of misunderstanding between hospital structures and departments	The risk of not receiving a timely diagnosis or treatment
The risk of wrong entry in the registers	The risk of prolonging the patient's illness
The risk of not understanding and misapplying the procedures	The risk of prolonging the patient's health
The risk of not having enough human resources	- The risk of prolonging the patient's illness
The risk regarding the impossibility of obtaining authorizations, approvals, membership certificates	- The risk of prolonging the patient's illness due to the impossibility of processing biological samples
The risk of not having funding	Risk of worsening patients' condition while waiting for service funding
The risk of not having service contracts	The risk of not receiving treatment on time
The risk of not having materials/reagents, etc. permanently in stock	The risk of not receiving treatment on time The risk of aggravation of the disease
The risk of exceeding the expiration date of the materials	The risk of not receiving a result on time The risk of receiving an erroneous result
Risks due to management factors	The risk of not receiving treatment on time The risk of aggravation of the disease

Risk of receiving reagents and dyes with reduced shelf life	The risk of receiving an erroneous result
Inconsistency between the products requested and those received	The risk of not receiving a timely diagnosis
Damage to the deceased due to transport or storage conditions	The risk of worsening and aggravating the mental state of the members

Managerial risks specific to Pathological Anatomy Services

Risk management in the healthcare system is used with the aim of organizing, coordinating and controlling the units providing medical services, so that they fulfill their predetermined objectives under conditions of managerial efficiency and effectiveness.

The managerial risks found in pathological anatomy services can be legal, IT, human resources, technical, labor protection, etc. And their nature, content, manifestations and incidence were presented in detail following the research undertaken by the collective in works that were published.

Synthetically, the managerial risks specific to a pathological anatomy service are presented in table no. 1 an original synthesis made by the authors of this paper, a novelty in the field of knowledge at the national and European level.

The analysis of managerial risks requires special attention on the part of any researcher or manager, because it has been observed that over time there are numerous changes in generating factors, intensities or atypical manifestations that can have positive influences on the management activity of the health unit, embodied in „ the well-being of the patient" but others, due to some negative consequences, must impose increased vigilance and an appropriate reactivity capacity at the level of decision-makers. These changes often require an action to reconfigure activities from a managerial, economic-financial point of view or a remodeling at the level of human resources on the beliefs and behaviors of medical personnel.

Case study on the influence of the pandemic on managerial and clinical risks and measures to prevent or eliminate risks in pathology laboratories

The Pathological Anatomy Service represents an interconnected branch of the health system, an indispensable link that ensures the histopathological diagnosis, an important diagnosis in the establishment of subsequent therapies.

Pathological anatomy" consists of medical activities according to operational procedures and standardized work protocols, which consists in the macroscopic and microscopic examination of biological products from both inpatients and outpatients, as well as from deceased persons.

In Romania, according to the legislation, every hospital unit with beds, be they municipal or county hospitals, is obliged to have a pathological anatomy service.

The present study was carried out in a pathological anatomy service in a health unit located in the Central area of Transylvania and whose beginnings are closely related to the establishment of the Institute of Medicine and Pharmacy in Cluj-Napoca. More precisely, this service was established in the form of a laboratory about 70 years ago, with elite professors at its helm.

This service falling within the legislative patterns, thus fulfilling the criteria of good functionality, can be found on the map of the top specialized services in pathological anatomy in Romania.

Being a modular hospital, the Pathological Anatomy Service has its location in a central area with extended addressability, containing only two compartments in the present location, respectively, the histopathology compartment and the cytology compartment, and the Prosecution compartment being located within the premises of a hospital that owns sections such as surgery and ATI, operating on the basis of some functional circuits, which are approved by the management of the health unit, respectively the SPIAAM Department.

These circuits have the role of providing a good functionality of the activity and at the same time of protecting the medical personnel as well as the patients - the circuit of the employed personnel, the circuit of biological samples, the circuit of waste from medical and non-medical activities, the circuit of specific documents, the circuit of underwear.

From the point of view of human resources, a total number of 25 employees work in this laboratory, of which: 6 doctors, of which 5 are doctors with clinical integration, having university degrees as lecturers and university professors, are specialized in different pathologies, following different courses on different pathologies, and their presence at various national and international scientific events, does nothing but enrich their knowledge, which they later put at the service of the patient, 8 laboratory assistants, 2 autopsies, 2 registrars and 2 cleaners.

The technology and the activity carried out at the level of the Pathological Anatomy Service

The equipment and instruments provided are specific to this branch of medicine, including equipment intended especially for service departments.

Like any activity that takes place in a public institution, the activity of the pathological anatomy service is carried out on the basis of system and operational procedures, in which the performance indicators are stipulated, which, by reaching them, reach the standards that each patient is empowered to meet have:

- The ratio between registered cases and those handed over to the owners;
- The ratio between registered and deceased cases;
- The time elapsed from the patient's death to the release to the next of kin;
- Respect by the health personnel of the procedure related to the transport and delivery of the deceased to their relatives;
- Completing and correctly registering transport documents;
- Numerical records of notifications;
- Numerical records regarding the management of the deceased.

Pandemic influences in the pathological anatomy laboratory

The changes generated by the pandemic were highlighted by the modification of the "daily lifestyle" of the laboratory, by the new measures taken at the health unit level. These strict measures were imperatively needed and implemented to limit the spread of the disease.

Specifically, mandatory measures were implemented at the laboratory level as follows:

Measures related to the category of procedural risks:

- Application of special instructions dedicated to health personnel;
- New instructions aimed at carrying out the activity during the pandemic, which mainly refer to:
 - o hand hygiene, mandatory use of protective clothing and protective equipment;
 - o Mandatory triage by checking the body temperature, drawing up a standardized form specifying certain parameters of the state of health and recording it in the Epidemiological Triage Register;
 - o Mandatory distancing at work.
- Drawing up or applying specific procedures;
- drawing up new system and operational procedures specific to the pandemic situation;
- Preventive measures and elimination of risks;
- The introduction of special procedures regarding the "Prosecution" compartment
- Ex. P.O. on the management of deceased patients at high risk of infection, with immediate applicability for SARS CoV - 2 virus infection.

Measures related to the category of economic risks:

- Changes related to the prioritization of purchases.
- Focusing procurement on hygiene products and protective equipment
- Equipping the Inquest department with modern medical equipment - mortuary refrigerator with four seats for deceased non-covid patients
- Equipping the Prosecution department with a refrigerated train in order to store deceased Covid-19 patients.

Measures related to the category of technical/technological risks:

- The computerization of the service through the transmission of intra-hospital documents through modern information systems, thus saving both the patients and the medical staff from unnecessary trips, emphasizing the fact that the new circuit of documents constitutes a strong point in efficiency.

Measures related to the category of legal risks:

- Implementation of new legal norms, methodologies and instructions, issued by competent bodies

Preventive measures and elimination of risks:

- Compliance with all circuits both at the laboratory level and at the sanitary unit level;
- Modification of the work schedule with hourly spacing;
- Temporary suspension of the Duty Report and other scientific events;
- Temporary isolation of employees with suspicious clinical manifestations indicating infection with the SARS CoV-2 virus;

Following the study carried out in the present laboratory, it can be noted an essential change in the way the laboratory worked, better said, this change negatively influenced both the patients and the medical staff. Thus, the following aspects were highlighted at the level of indicators:

- the considerable reduction of histopathological cases from the hospital wards, this is due to stopping hospitalizations in clinical and non-clinical wards, but a notable thing is the increase in deaths caused not only by the virus, but also by pathologies that were not treated in time and were postponed, this aspect can be observed in table no. 2. which shows us a picture of the frequency of cases in day and continuous hospitalization in the health unit.

Table no. 2. Analysis of the cases investigated in the analyzed service

Year	Day hospitalization	Continuous hospitalization
2021	267,410.00	575,740.00
2020	135,910.00	449,850.00
2019	366,840.00	841,390.00

If we analyze the ratio between the cases registered (processed) in the pathological anatomy service and those who died according to table no. 3, we will be able to practically demonstrate the influence of the Covid-19 pandemic on the activity in the laboratory, in which it is evident that the number of histopathology cases has decreased drastically compared to previous years, but at the same time the cases of death have increased.

An aspect that can be perceived as positive is the granting of incentives for the period of the state of emergency due to the pandemic and which came to support the health personnel, being the risk incentive according to art. 8/ O.U.G. no. 43/2020 for the approval of some support measures settled from European funds, as a result of the response to Covid-19, during the state of emergency, amendments and additions through O.U.G. no. 64/ 2020 in which the personnel who managed the cases of Covid-19 death were remunerated with an amount of 2500 lei.

Table no. 3. Analysis of histopathological cases and deaths during the pandemic

Year	Histopathologic al cases	Death cases
2018	8135	514
2019	8294	594
2020	4286	619
2021	6042	659

It should be mentioned that, since the staff of the pathological anatomy service is not regulated by the number of cases, we can say that there were no negative influences during this period.

It is obvious that with the onset of the pandemic, the factors that contributed to the success or failure of the response to this "pandemic crisis" were highlighted. Although this pandemic has been a test of resistance in which human dignity has been put to the test, in which some voices of public opinion are questioning, for example, the quarantine is fully justified from the point of view of human rights.

At the level of the branch of pathological anatomy, during the pandemic, certain changes were observed that affected both patients and health personnel. All these changes in structure brought consequences of insecurity and dissatisfaction for patients and medical professionals in which clinical risks experienced an increasing dynamic. The presence of seasonal fluctuations in which the cases of death increased alarmingly and the cases of surgical treatment of some patients were downright suppressed, contributed to the modification of the map of clinical and managerial risks.

It is easy to understand that in extreme situations, the best measures to protect health must be imposed. Following the analysis, we identified both negative and positive experiences. Among the negative experiences following the activity carried out in the pathological anatomy laboratory, we mention the following:

1. the imposition of distance between medical personnel at work and the establishment of home isolation of some employees following infection with the SARS CoV-2 virus, which led to a reduction in the number of personnel, making the work process more difficult;
2. the physical and mental overwork of the staff in the Prosecution department, due to the numerous cases of deceased patients;
3. Exposure of medical personnel to the possibility of infection with the SARS CoV - 2 virus;
4. Considerable reduction of cases resulting from surgical and non-surgical interventions;
5. The alarming increase in the number of deaths;
6. Estimating the need for materials in order to manage the activity of managing deceased patients presents difficulties;
7. Pressure on the medical staff from the relatives.

Positive experiences:

1. Use of the computer system at maximum capacity regarding the route of documents;
2. Obtaining funds for the purchase of sanitary materials;
3. Financial benefits of medical personnel directly involved in the management of deceased patients;
4. Greater attention to the use of protective equipment;

As a result of the blockage regarding access to medical care in which many social inequities were identified, the impact of the pandemic on the health system was unprecedented, moreover in all medical sectors, including it left its mark in the pathological anatomy laboratory.

In this context, I propose that in the future, taking into account the good progress of the laboratory's activity, the intensification of the activity in the IT field, by expanding the IT system and in the technical area of processing biological samples, as well as the correct use of protective equipment within the service.

Conclusions

Following theoretical and applied research, we can observe certain changes that have affected both patients and health personnel. All these changes in structure brought consequences of insecurity and dissatisfaction for patients and medical professionals in which clinical risks experienced an increasing dynamic.

Thus, following the theoretical research carried out, it is highlighted that in pathological anatomy services there are risks falling into two categories, clinical risks and managerial risks.

The managerial risks specific to a pathological anatomy service have been brought to light and are presented in this paper in the form of an original synthesis made by the authors of this paper, representing a novelty in the field of knowledge at a national and European level

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